

APPLYING LIU'S METHOD FOR CHARACTERIZING MELT DIMENSIONS AND FLUENCE THRESHOLD IN LPBF

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ABSTRACT: In Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF) it is critical to have precise control of the laser parameters for achieving high-quality components, particularly in intricate lattice structures where optimal energy input is essential to prevent defects. This research explores determining the minimum irradiation fluence needed to initiate material modification and the diameter of the heat source using the experimental Liu's method. Single-point experiments were conducted on an LPBF platform using three different powder metal alloys, varying the laser energy input. Microscope measurements were employed to analyze how laser energy affects material response. The outcomes offer empirical insights into calculating fluence thresholds and resolving melt spot sizes based on energy input for each material tested. These findings provide practical insights for optimizing the LPBF process, aiding in the precise fabrication of complex geometries and lattice structures that demand controlled melt spot sizes and melting behavior.

KEYWORDS: laser powder bed fusion, Liu's method, fluence, melt spot size

1 INTRODUCTION

Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF) has developed as a leading metal additive manufacturing technology, offering high flexibility in fabricating complex three-dimensional components with lattice structures. LPBF uses a high-power laser beam to selectively melt and fuse together successive layers of metal powder to build a three-dimensional part (Gibson et al., 2021). Fig. 1 shows a schematic demonstration of the workflow of the LPBF process. The LPBF process begins with a thin layer of metal powder being spread evenly over a build plate. A laser beam is then directed onto the powder layer, selectively melting and fusing together the powder particles according to a 3D model. After each layer is completed, the build plate is lowered by one layer thickness, and a new layer of powder is spread over the previous layer. This process is repeated layer by layer until the part is complete. During the LPBF process, the laser beam heats the metal powder to a temperature close to its melting point, causing it to melt and solidify as it cools. The process is carried out in a controlled atmosphere of

inert gas to prevent oxidation of the metal. This results in a fully dense, high-strength metal part with excellent mechanical properties.

The selection of nominal process parameters is important factor in achieving the melt size needed and ensuring the quality of the fabricated part (Ahmed et al., 2022; Simson & Subbu, 2022). This aspect becomes even more crucial when printing intricate geometries characteristic for lattice designs (Erturk et al., 2022). Hence, attention to the delivered laser energy input is crucial for achieving controlled melting dynamics and dimensional accuracy (Vasileska et al., 2022). The fluence threshold, defined as the minimum energy per unit area required to initiate material modification or melting, represents a critical parameter in understanding the laser-material interaction dynamics during LPBF. By precisely characterizing the fluence threshold, researchers and engineers can optimize laser processing parameters to achieve desired material properties and part geometries while minimizing defects and process uncertainties (Großmann et al., 2019).

Fig. 1 Schematic demonstration of LPBF process

However, the fluence cannot be directly measured and assessed, as it requires characterizing both the integrated laser pulse energy and its spatial distribution. Moreover, its theoretical calculation is challenging due to unknown parameters during laser irradiation, such as reflectivity, conductivity, dielectric constant, density, and expansion coefficient, which vary significantly during the laser irradiation and are difficult to quantify accurately (Torrise et al., 2007). The Liu's method, also known as the D-squared method, has become a powerful tool for experimentally determining the fluence threshold in laser processing applications (Liu, 1982). The method interprets the material's threshold response to laser pulse irradiation as a direct reflection of the laser profile. By examining the melting shape of the modification due to laser-material interaction generated at various pulse energies, the method associates the modification limits to a local fluence, representing the fluence threshold for modification initiation. Although Liu originally developed this method to empirically determine the diameter of a Gaussian laser beam, its practical application extends to accurately determining the modification fluence threshold of any material exposed to laser pulses. Through single-point laser irradiation experiments, the method characterizes the relationship between laser energy input and material response, enabling determination of the fluence threshold and melt size of the material under consideration (Chang & Tu, 2012). The melt size of the material modification induced by laser irradiation is critical in LPBF processes as it directly impacts the resolution, surface finish, and dimensional accuracy of the fabricated parts. Understanding and controlling the melt size are essential for achieving high-fidelity fabrication, particularly in applications requiring fine features, intricate geometries, or lattice structures (Vasileska et al., 2020).

Liu's method has been commonly used in research works for laser ablation process to investigate the ablation fluency threshold (Schell et al., 2022), and the interference diameter (Hariharan et al., 2024).

This paper shows the application of Liu's method for fluency threshold and heat source diameter estimation employed in LPBF. Firstly, a theoretical overview of the method is provided. Then, an experiment is proposed with varied energy input and measurements of the melt spot diameters were collected. The findings include the results of model fitting and discussions on fluence threshold and heat source diameter estimation.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND OF LIU'S METHOD

Liu's method, also known as the D-square method, offers a straightforward experimental approach for determining the fluence modification threshold by measuring the sizes of induced modifications at various irradiation energies. An assumption for applying the method is that the laser beam profile follows a Gaussian distribution. Mathematically, this methodology is expressed by the equation:

$$F(r) = F_0 \cdot e^{-2r^2/w_0^2} \quad (1)$$

where $F(r)$ represents the local fluence at a radial position r , F_0 is the peak fluence value, and $2 \cdot w_0 = D_0$ denotes the heat source diameter at $1/e^2$ the peak value. The schematic depiction of a Gaussian laser beam profile with the designated measurement of the heat source diameter D_0 is illustrated in Fig. 2. Liu's method, based on the assumption of a deterministic material modification behavior, defines the fluence threshold, F_{th} , as the local fluence corresponding to the border of the crater, where its radius is equal to R . Thus, the expression is given by:

$$F_{th} = F_0 \cdot e^{-2R^2/w_0^2} \quad (2)$$

The expression that can be linearized by taking its logarithm, resulting in:

$$R^2 = \frac{w_0^2}{2} \cdot \ln\left(\frac{F_0}{F_{th}}\right) \quad (3)$$

However, the experimental parameter typically measured is not the peak fluence but rather the integrated pulse energy delivered during the laser spot exposure on the material, denoted as E . In the case of typical squared wave emission profiles with modulated emission in the μs regime, the single pulse energy E corresponds to the product of the peak power P and the exposure time t_{on} :

$$E = P \cdot t_{on} \quad (4)$$

Then, E can be derived from F_0 as follows:

$$F_0 = \frac{2 \cdot E}{\pi \cdot w_0^2} \quad (5)$$

With the energy input threshold E_{th} defined as the minimum pulse energy required for material modification initiation, the calculation of the fluence threshold is conducted as follows:

$$F_{th} = \frac{2 \cdot E_{th}}{\pi \cdot w_0^2} \quad (6)$$

By substituting Equation 5 and Equation 6 into Equation 3, the relationship between the observables R and E is established as follows:

Fig. 2 Gaussian laser beam profile illustration: a) in x-z plane; b) in x-y plane

$$R^2 = \frac{w_0^2}{2} \cdot \ln\left(\frac{E}{E_{th}}\right) \quad (7)$$

When utilizing diameter values of the laser-induced melt spots on the material, the equation can be expressed in the following manner which constitutes the fundamental aspect of the Liu's method:

$$D^2 = 2 \cdot w_0^2 \cdot \ln\left(\frac{E}{E_{th}}\right) \quad (8)$$

Liu's method suggests plotting $\ln(E)$ values on the x-axis and D^2 values on the y-axis. Consequently, the Gaussian beam waist diameter D_0 is determined through the slope of a linear regression. Moreover, the energy threshold value E_{th} can be obtained from the x-axis intercept. Subsequently, the laser fluence threshold value F_{th} is easily calculated by applying Equation 6 using these two obtained values.

3 EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

3.1 Experimental setup

The laser exposure experiments were carried out on an open LPBF platform employing a single-mode fiber laser (IPG Photonics YLR-300-AC-Y11, Cambridge, MA, USA), emitting at a wavelength of 1070 nm. The laser source can emit in pulse wave regime in order to obtain laser pulses with varying exposure times, with a peak power output of 300W.

3.2 Experimental setup

Three powder materials were tested: AISI316L, Ti-6Al-4V, and Zn-0.5Mg alloy. These metal alloys were deliberately selected due to their widespread industrial applications, as they are commonly utilized in critical sectors such as aerospace, automotive, and biomedical industries (Gupta et al., 2022; Lannunziata et al., 2022; Lietaert et al., 2020; Rossi et al., 2023). Experiments were performed with six levels of laser energy (E), achieved by varying the peak

power (P) across two levels (200 W and 150 W) and adjusting the pulse duration (ton) across three levels (800 μ s, 400 μ s, and 200 μ s). This resulted in six energy levels (0.16, 0.12, 0.08, 0.06, 0.04, and 0.03 J). Each experimental condition was replicated three times, leading to a total of 18 laser spot exposures per material. The fixed and varied parameters are outlined in

Table 1. Fixed and variable parameters used in the experiment

Fixed parameters	Values
Powder layer height [μ m]	50
Variable parameters	Values
Material	AISI316L, Ti-6Al-4V, Zn-0.5Mg
Laser power, P [W]	150-200
Laser exposure time, ton [μ s]	200-400-800

The rationale for altering both parameters that influence the energy input (P and ton), rather than just to achieve the needed value of E by changing only one, was to investigate if either parameter individually influenced the outcome. However, the results indicated that whether the variation in E stemmed from changes of P or of ton, the response remained unaffected. Instead, the melting behavior of the material was influenced only by the collective energy input of the laser.

3.3 MEASUREMENT

The experimental samples were captured using an optical microscope, followed by automated estimation of the diameter using an algorithm written in the software MATLAB (The MathWorks, Inc., Massachusetts, USA). The algorithm first identifies the largest possible inscribed circle within the sample spot and then calculates its diameter. This automated measurement method reduces

human error and excludes stuck powder particles on the circumference of the melt spot. Examples of the laser melt spots for the three materials are presented in Table 2, showcasing spots obtained with maximum energy input (0.16 J) and minimum energy input (0.03 J).

Table 2. Examples of melt spots dimensions as function of materials and energy input levels

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Employing Liu's method on the gathered experimental information, the graphs depicted in **Error! Reference source not found.** show $\ln(E)$ values on the x-axis and D^2 values on the y-axis. The resulting graphical fitting of Liu's analytical model (Eq. 8) is displayed in the figure, along with the confidence interval (CI) and prediction interval (PI) of the fitting. It can be observed that the majority of data points belong within the prediction interval, validating the fitting of the regression model. Moreover, the figures illustrate the coefficients of determination R^2 for the model fitting across the three materials, demonstrating a high goodness of fit. Additionally, the lack-of-fit test yielded non-significant results.

The regression line for AISI316L is as follows:

$$D^2 = 0.09903 + 0.02330 \cdot \ln E \quad (9)$$

The regression line for Ti-6Al-4V is as follows:

$$D^2 = 0.1862 + 0.04622 \cdot \ln E \quad (10)$$

The regression line for Zn-0.5Mg is as follows:

$$D^2 = 0.1066 + 0.02515 \cdot \ln E \quad (11)$$

Based on the linear regression model fitting and Eq. 8, the model coefficients enable estimation of the energy threshold value E_{th} , as well as heat source diameter at $1/e^2$ the peak value D_0 . Evidently, the linear regression lines of the three materials are different since the E_{th} as the minimum

energy needed to start material modification is a characteristic dependent on the considered material. Moreover, the fluency threshold value F_{th} can be calculated from Eq. 6. The results for the three materials are shown in the following

Table 3. Results of E_{th} , D_0 and F_{th} estimation with Liu's method for the three materials

	AISI316L	Ti-6Al-4V	Zn-0.5Mg
D_0 [μm]	215.870	304.039	224.277
E_{th} [J]	0.014	0.018	0.014
F_{th} [J/cm ²]	77.970	49.059	73.081

It can be seen that Ti-6Al-4V exhibits a higher energy input threshold compared to the other materials, indicating that to start melting a higher laser energy is required. This disparity can be rationalized by the higher melting point of the titanium alloy compared to the other materials. Additionally, examining the fluency threshold shows that Ti-6Al-4V requires a lower fluence, implying less energy per unit area for initiating melting. When equivalent energy levels were applied, the Ti-6Al-4V alloy displayed a larger spot size compared to the other materials. This can be attributed to the fact that Ti-6Al-4V has higher absorption coefficient, meaning that it absorbs the laser energy more efficiently which in terms affects how it responds to laser irradiation. Consequently, this property impacts the heat distribution within the material, thereby affecting both the size of the melting spot and the energy per unit area required. Thus, while the Ti-6Al-4V alloy demands more total energy to start melting, it disperses this energy over a larger area, necessitating less energy per unit area for melting initiation compared to the other materials.

By means of the regression equations, it is possible to calculate the predicted melting spot size attained with a specific energy input. Understanding the relationship between melt size and energy input is particularly critical in the fabrication of intricate lattice structures, where precise spot resolution and controlled melting behavior are necessary.

It is worth noting that while Liu's method has been extensively used in literature, its validity hinges on the requirement that the laser interacting with the target has a perfectly Gaussian beam profile. Hence, an assumption for the fluence analysis is that the irradiation beam is perfectly Gaussian. However, imperfections in the beam from laser systems or practical optical setups can introduce dispersion in the fluence results obtained using this method (Garcia-Lechuga & Grojo, 2021). Additionally, it is observed that the heat source

diameter is estimated with different values for the three materials and is also estimated larger the laser beam diameter employed in the process. This observation suggests that heat transfer mechanisms during laser-material interaction may not be entirely negligible in the LPBF process. Moreover, sintered particles around the melted region can be present which may adhere to the neighboring particles. Despite these limitations, the method offers an analytical thermal model that has demonstrated its usefulness in empirically characterizing the laser beam profile and the material fluence thresholds.

Fig. 3 Graphical representation of Liu's regression fit with 95% confidence (CI) and prediction intervals (PI) of the materials: a) AISI316L; b) Ti-6Al-4V; c) Zn-0.5Mg

5 CONCLUSIONS

The study provides practical insights into the determination of fluence threshold and melt size in LPBF using the Liu's or D-squared method, by analyzing the laser-material interactions in three powder metal alloys. A specifically designed experiment was conducted where the energy input was varied and measurements of the melt spot diameters were collected. The fitting of Liu's analytical model showed high accuracy. The material-specific characteristics, especially the material's melting point and absorption coefficient, led to variations in the model coefficients, affecting the resulting fluence threshold and the diameter of the heat source at 1/e2 of the peak value across different materials. The model furthermore offers a method to compute melt size as a function of the delivered laser energy, which is particularly important when producing intricate structures to ensure precise control over the melting spot. However, it's essential to acknowledge limitations when applying the method, including the assumption of a perfect Gaussian beam profile and the neglect of certain heat transfer mechanisms during laser-material interaction.

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